

Improving Electricity and Natural Gas Systems Coordination Using Swing Option Contracts

Conor O'Malley, Stefanos Delikaraoglou and Gabriela Hug
Power Systems Laboratory, ETH Zurich, Switzerland,
{omalleyc, delikaraoglou, hug}@eeh.ee.ethz.ch

Abstract

This document serves as an electronic companion for the paper 'Improving Electricity and Natural Gas Systems Coordination Using Swing Option Contracts'. It contains provide supplemental material for to the mathematical formulation of the problem and data that is used for the case study.

1 MPEC Formulation of Contract Pricing Problem

To solve the bilevel optimization problem, it is recast as a mathematical program with equilibrium constraints. This is done by replacing each of the lower level problems with their KKT system which consists of the original constraints, the stationarity conditions and the complementarity conditions.

1.1 Stochastic Electricity Dispatch Model

We start by restating the lower level problem for the electricity dispatch model.

$$\begin{aligned}
\underset{\Xi^{\text{DUE}} \cup \Xi^{\text{RT}}}{\text{Minimize}} \quad C_e^{\text{exp}} = & \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i p_{it} + \sum_{i \in I^{\text{G}}} \left(\sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g, t}^g \eta_i p_{it} + \sum_c \sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \lambda_{n_g, c}^c \eta_i p_{ict}^c \right) \right] + \\
& \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \pi_\omega \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i \left(\psi_i^+ p_{i\omega t}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{i\omega t}^- \right) + \right. \\
& \sum_{i \in I^{\text{G}}} \left[\sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g, \omega t}^g \eta_i \left(\psi_i^+ p_{i\omega t}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{i\omega t}^- \right) + \right. \\
& \left. \left. \sum_c \sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g, c}^c \eta_i \left(p_{ic\omega t}^{c+} - p_{ic\omega t}^{c-} \right) \right] + C^{\text{sh}, e} l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{1a}$$

subject to

$$w_t + \sum_{i \in I} (p_{it} + p_{ict}^c) = D_t : \lambda_t^e, \quad \forall t, \tag{2a}$$

$$0 \leq w_t \leq \bar{w} : \underline{\mu}_t^w, \bar{\mu}_t^w, \quad \forall t, \tag{2b}$$

$$p_{it} + r_{it}^+ \leq \bar{p}_i - \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \bar{p}_{ic}^c : \bar{\mu}_{it}^p, \quad \forall i, t, \tag{2c}$$

$$0 \leq p_{it} - r_{it}^- : \underline{\mu}_{it}^p, \quad \forall i, t, \tag{2d}$$

$$\sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \underline{p}_{ic}^c \leq p_{ict}^c \leq \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \bar{p}_{ic}^c : \underline{\nu}_{ict}, \bar{\nu}_{ict}, \forall i, t, c, \tag{2e}$$

$$0 \leq r_{ict}^{c+} \leq u_c \bar{p}_{ic}^c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} - p_{ict}^c : \underline{\nu}_{ict}^+, \bar{\nu}_{ict}^+, \quad \forall i, c, t, \tag{2f}$$

$$0 \leq r_{ict}^{c-} \leq p_{ict}^c - u_c \underline{p}_{ic}^c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} : \underline{\nu}_{ict}^-, \bar{\nu}_{ict}^-, \quad \forall i, c, t, \tag{2g}$$

$$\sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \leq 1, \quad \forall i, t, \tag{2h}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{i \in I} (p_{i\omega t}^+ - p_{i\omega t}^- + p_{i\omega t}^{c+} - p_{i\omega t}^{c-}) + W_{\omega t} - w_t \\
& - w_{\omega t}^{\text{spill}} + l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} = 0 : \lambda_{\omega t}^e, \quad \forall \omega, t,
\end{aligned} \tag{2i}$$

$$0 \leq p_{i\omega t}^+ \leq r_{it}^+ : \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+}, \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+}, \quad \forall i, \omega, t, \tag{2j}$$

$$0 \leq p_{i\omega t}^- \leq r_{it}^- : \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-}, \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-}, \quad \forall i, \omega, t, \tag{2k}$$

$$0 \leq p_{ic\omega t}^{c+} \leq r_{ict}^{c+} : \underline{\mu}_{ic\omega t}^{c+}, \bar{\mu}_{ic\omega t}^{c+}, \quad \forall i, c, \omega, t, \tag{2l}$$

$$0 \leq p_{ic\omega t}^{c-} \leq r_{ict}^{c-} : \underline{\mu}_{ic\omega t}^{c-}, \bar{\mu}_{ic\omega t}^{c-}, \quad \forall i, c, \omega, t, \tag{2m}$$

$$0 \leq w_{\omega t}^{\text{spill}} \leq W_{\omega t} : \underline{\mu}_{\omega t}^w, \bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^w, \quad \forall t, \omega, \tag{2n}$$

$$0 \leq l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} \leq D_t^e : \underline{\mu}_{\omega t}^l, \bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^l, \quad \forall t, \omega, \tag{2o}$$

1.1.1 Stationarity Conditions

Next the stationarity conditions for each of the day-ahead and real-time variables are derived.

Day-ahead variables

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it} = C_i - \lambda_t^e + \bar{\mu}_{it}^p - \underline{\mu}_{it}^p = 0 \quad , \forall t, i \in I^{NG} \quad (3a)$$

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it} = \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_i^{NG}} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g t}^g \eta_i - \lambda_t^e + \bar{\mu}_{it}^p - \underline{\mu}_{it}^p = 0 \quad , \forall t, i \in I^G \quad (3b)$$

$$\partial L/\partial p_{itc}^c = \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_i^{NG}} \lambda_{n_g c}^c \eta_i - \lambda_t^e + \bar{\nu}_{ict} - \underline{\nu}_{ict} \quad (3c)$$

$$+ \bar{\nu}_{ict}^+ - \underline{\nu}_{ict}^+ + \bar{\nu}_{ict}^- - \underline{\nu}_{ict}^- = 0 \quad , \forall t, c, i \in I^G \quad (3d)$$

$$\partial L/\partial w_t = -\lambda_t^E + \bar{\mu}_t^w - \underline{\mu}_t^w + \sum_{\omega} \lambda_{\omega t}^E = 0 \quad , \forall t \quad (3e)$$

$$\partial L/\partial r_{it}^+ = \bar{\mu}_{it}^p - \sum_{\omega} \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+} = 0 \quad , \forall t, i \quad (3f)$$

$$\partial L/\partial r_{it}^- = \underline{\mu}_{it}^p - \sum_{\omega} \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-} = 0 \quad , \forall t, i \quad (3g)$$

$$\partial L/\partial r_{ict}^{c+} = \bar{\nu}_{ict}^+ - \underline{\nu}_{ict}^+ - \sum_{\omega} \bar{\mu}_{ic\omega t}^{c+} = 0 \quad , \forall t, c, i \in I^G \quad (3h)$$

$$\partial L/\partial r_{ict}^{c-} = \bar{\nu}_{ict}^- - \underline{\nu}_{ict}^- - \sum_{\omega} \bar{\mu}_{ic\omega t}^{c-} = 0 \quad , \forall t, c, i \in I^G \quad (3i)$$

Real-time variables

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it\omega}^+ = \pi_{\omega} C_i \psi_i^+ - \lambda_{\omega t}^E + \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+} - \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+} = 0 \quad , \forall t, \omega, i \in I^{NG} \quad (4a)$$

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it\omega}^- = -\pi_{\omega} C_i \psi_i^- + \lambda_{\omega t}^E + \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-} - \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-} = 0 \quad , \forall t, \omega, i \in I^{NG} \quad (4b)$$

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it\omega}^+ = \pi_{\omega} \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_i^{NG}} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g \omega t}^g \eta_i \psi_i^+ - \lambda_{\omega t}^E + \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+} - \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+} = 0 \quad , \forall t, \omega, i \in I^G \quad (4c)$$

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it\omega}^- = -\pi_{\omega} \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_i^{NG}} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g \omega t}^g \eta_i \psi_i^- + \lambda_{\omega t}^E + \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-} - \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-} = 0 \quad , \forall t, \omega, i \in I^G \quad (4d)$$

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it\omega}^{c+} = \pi_{\omega} \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_i^{NG}} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g c}^c \eta_i - \lambda_{\omega t}^E + \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{c+} - \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{c+} = 0 \quad , \forall t, c, \omega, i \in I^G \quad (4e)$$

$$\partial L/\partial p_{it\omega}^{c-} = -\pi_{\omega} \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_i^{NG}} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g c}^c \eta_i + \lambda_{\omega t}^E + \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{c-} - \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{c-} = 0 \quad , \forall t, c, \omega, i \in I^G \quad (4f)$$

$$\partial L/\partial w_{t\omega}^{\text{spill}} = \lambda_{\omega t}^e + \bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^w - \underline{\mu}_{\omega t}^w = 0 \quad , \forall t, \omega \quad (4g)$$

$$\partial L/\partial t_{\omega}^{\text{sh}} = \pi_{\omega} C^{\text{sh},e} - \lambda_{\omega t}^e + \bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^l - \underline{\mu}_{\omega t}^l = 0 \quad , \forall t, \omega \quad (4h)$$

1.1.2 Complementarity Constraints

Lastly, the complementarity constraints are written as

Day-ahead variables

$$0 \leq (\bar{w} - w_t) \perp \bar{\mu}_t^w \geq 0, \quad \forall t \quad (5a)$$

$$0 \leq w_t \perp \underline{\mu}_t^w \geq 0, \quad \forall t \quad (5b)$$

$$0 \leq (\bar{p}_i - \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \bar{p}_{ic}^c - (p_{it} + r_{it}^+)) \perp \bar{\mu}_{it}^p \geq 0, \quad \forall i, t \quad (5c)$$

$$0 \leq (p_{it} - r_{it}^-) \perp \underline{\mu}_{it}^p \geq 0, \quad \forall i, t \quad (5d)$$

$$0 \leq \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \bar{p}_{ic}^c - p_{ict}^c \perp \bar{\nu}_{ict} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t \quad (5e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{ict}^c - \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \underline{p}_{ic}^c \perp \underline{\nu}_{ict} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t \quad (5f)$$

$$0 \leq \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \bar{p}_{ic}^c - p_{ict}^c - r_{itc}^{c+} \perp \bar{\nu}_{ict}^+ \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t \quad (5g)$$

$$0 \leq r_{itc}^{c+} \perp \underline{\nu}_{ict}^+ \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t \quad (5h)$$

$$0 \leq p_{ict}^c - \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}} \bar{p}_{ic}^c - r_{itc}^{c-} \perp \bar{\nu}_{ict}^- \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t \quad (5i)$$

$$0 \leq r_{itc}^{c-} \perp \underline{\nu}_{ict}^- \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t \quad (5j)$$

Real-time variables

$$0 \leq (r_{it}^+ - p_{i\omega t}^+) \perp \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, t, \omega \quad (6a)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i\omega t}^+ \perp \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p+} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, t, \omega \quad (6b)$$

$$0 \leq (r_{it}^- - p_{i\omega t}^-) \perp \bar{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, t, \omega \quad (6c)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i\omega t}^- \perp \underline{\mu}_{it\omega}^{p-} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, t, \omega \quad (6d)$$

$$0 \leq (r_{ict}^{c+} - p_{ic\omega t}^{c+}) \perp \bar{\mu}_{ict\omega}^{c+} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t, \omega \quad (6e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{ic\omega t}^{c+} \perp \underline{\mu}_{itc\omega}^{c+} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t, \omega \quad (6f)$$

$$0 \leq (r_{ict}^{c-} - p_{ic\omega t}^{c-}) \perp \bar{\mu}_{ict\omega}^{c-} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t, \omega \quad (6g)$$

$$0 \leq p_{ic\omega t}^{c-} \perp \underline{\mu}_{itc\omega}^{c-} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, c, t, \omega \quad (6h)$$

$$0 \leq (W_{\omega t} - w_{\omega t}^{\text{spill}}) \perp \bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^w \geq 0, \quad \forall t, \omega \quad (6i)$$

$$0 \leq w_{\omega t}^{\text{spill}} \perp \underline{\mu}_{\omega t}^w \geq 0, \quad \forall t, \omega \quad (6j)$$

$$0 \leq (D_t - l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}}) \perp \bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^l \geq 0, \quad \forall t, \omega \quad (6k)$$

$$0 \leq l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} \perp \underline{\mu}_{\omega t}^l \geq 0, \quad \forall t, \omega \quad (6l)$$

The KKT system for the electricity system dispatch is given by (3)-(6)

1.2 Gas Day-Ahead

The gas day-ahead KKT is derived in a similar fashion.

$$\text{Minimize}_{\Phi^D} C_g^D = \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{j \in J} C_j g_j \quad (7a)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^J} g_{jt} + \sum_{\ell} \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{\Lambda} q_{\ell t} = D_{n_g t}^g + \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_{i_g} (p_{it}^* + p_{it}^{c*}) : \lambda_{n_g t}^g, \quad \forall n_g, t, \quad (8a)$$

$$0 \leq g_{jt} \leq \bar{g}_j, \quad \forall j : \underline{\mu}_{jt}^g, \bar{\mu}_{jt}^g, \quad \forall j, t, \quad (8b)$$

$$0 \leq q_{\ell t} \leq \bar{q}_{\ell} : \underline{\mu}_{\ell t}^q, \bar{\mu}_{\ell t}^q, \quad \forall \ell \in \Lambda^P, t, \quad (8c)$$

1.2.1 Stationarity Conditions

$$\partial L / \partial g_{jt} = C_j - \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_w^{Ng}} \lambda_{n_g t}^g + \bar{\mu}_{jt}^g - \underline{\mu}_{jt}^g = 0, \quad \forall j, t, \quad (9a)$$

$$\partial L / \partial q_{\ell t} = - \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_{\ell}^{ng}} \lambda_{n_g t}^g + \bar{\mu}_{\ell t}^q - \underline{\mu}_{\ell t}^q = 0, \quad \forall \ell, t, \quad (9b)$$

1.2.2 Complementarity Conditions

$$0 \leq (\bar{g}_j - g_{jt}) \perp \bar{\mu}_{jt}^g \geq 0, \quad \forall j, t \quad (10a)$$

$$0 \leq (g_{jt}) \perp \underline{\mu}_{jt}^g \geq 0, \quad \forall j, t \quad (10b)$$

$$0 \leq (\bar{q}_{\ell} - q_{\ell t}) \perp \bar{\mu}_{\ell t}^q \geq 0, \quad \forall \ell, t \quad (10c)$$

$$0 \leq (q_{\ell t}) \perp \underline{\mu}_{\ell t}^q \geq 0, \quad \forall \ell, t \quad (10d)$$

$$(10e)$$

The KKT system for the Gas Day-ahead problem is given by (8)-(10)

1.3 Gas Real-Time

$$\text{Minimize}_{\Phi_{\omega'}^{\text{RT}}} \mathcal{C}_{g,\omega}^{\text{RT}} = \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{j \in J} (C_j^+ g_{j\omega't}^+ - C_j^- g_{j\omega't}^-) + \sum_{n_g \in N^G} C^{\text{sh},g} l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh},g} \right] \quad (11a)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^J} (g_{jt\omega'}^+ - g_{jt\omega'}^-) - \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_{i_g} \Delta p_{i\omega't}^* + l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh},G} - \sum_{\ell} \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{\Lambda} (q_{\ell t}^* - \tilde{q}_{\ell\omega't}) = 0 : \tilde{\lambda}_{n_g\omega't}^g, \quad \forall n_g, t, \quad (12a)$$

$$0 \leq g_{j\omega't}^+ \leq \bar{g}_j - g_{jt}^* : \underline{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g+}, \bar{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g+}, \quad \forall j, t, \quad (12b)$$

$$0 \leq g_{j\omega't}^- \leq g_{jt}^* : \underline{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g-}, \bar{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g-}, \quad \forall j, t, \quad (12c)$$

$$0 \leq \tilde{q}_{\ell\omega't} \leq \bar{q}_{\ell} : \underline{\tilde{\mu}}_{\ell\omega't}^q, \bar{\tilde{\mu}}_{\ell\omega't}^q, \quad \forall \ell \in \Lambda^P, t, \quad (12d)$$

$$0 \leq l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh},G} \leq D_{n_g t}^G : \underline{\mu}_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh}}, \bar{\mu}_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh}}, \quad \forall n_g, t, \quad (12e)$$

1.3.1 Stationarity Conditions

$$\partial L / \partial g_{jt\omega'}^+ = C_j^+ - \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_{\omega'}^{Ng}} \tilde{\lambda}_{n_g\omega't}^g + \bar{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g+} - \underline{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g+} = 0, \quad \forall \omega', t, \omega', \quad (13a)$$

$$\partial L / \partial g_{jt\omega'}^- = -C_j^- + \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_{\omega'}^{Ng}} \tilde{\lambda}_{n_g\omega't}^g + \bar{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g-} - \underline{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g-} = 0, \quad \forall \omega', t, \omega', \quad (13b)$$

$$\partial L / \partial \tilde{q}_{\ell\omega't} = - \sum_{n_g \in \mathcal{M}_{\omega'}^{Ng}} + \tilde{\lambda}_{n_g\omega't}^g + \bar{\mu}_{\ell\omega't}^q - \underline{\tilde{\mu}}_{\ell\omega't}^q = 0, \quad \forall \ell, t, \omega', \quad (13c)$$

$$\partial L / \partial l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh}} = C^{\text{sh},g} - \tilde{\lambda}_{n_g\omega't}^g + \bar{\mu}_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh}} - \underline{\mu}_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh}} = 0, \quad \forall n_g, t, \omega', \quad (13d)$$

1.3.2 Complementarity Conditions

$$0 \leq (\bar{g}_j - g_{jt}^* - g_{j\omega't}^+) \perp \bar{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g+} \geq 0, \quad \forall j, \omega', t \quad (14a)$$

$$0 \leq (g_{j\omega't}^+) \perp \underline{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g+} \geq 0, \quad \forall j, \omega', t \quad (14b)$$

$$0 \leq (g_{jt}^* - g_{j\omega't}^-) \perp \bar{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g-} \geq 0, \quad \forall j, \omega', t \quad (14c)$$

$$0 \leq (g_{j\omega't}^-) \perp \underline{\mu}_{j\omega't}^{g-} \geq 0, \quad \forall j, \omega', t \quad (14d)$$

$$0 \leq (\bar{q}_{\ell} - \tilde{q}_{\ell\omega't}) \perp \bar{\tilde{\mu}}_{\ell\omega't}^q \geq 0, \quad \forall \ell, \omega', t \quad (14e)$$

$$0 \leq (\tilde{q}_{\ell\omega't}) \perp \underline{\tilde{\mu}}_{\ell\omega't}^q \geq 0, \quad \forall \ell, \omega', t \quad (14f)$$

$$0 \leq (D_{n_g t}^G - l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh},G}) \perp \bar{\mu}_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh}} \geq 0, \quad \forall \ell, \omega', t \quad (14g)$$

$$0 \leq (l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh},G}) \perp \underline{\mu}_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh}} \geq 0, \quad \forall \ell, \omega', t \quad (14h)$$

The KKT system for the Gas Day-ahead problem is given by (12)-(14)

1.4 Linearizing the Objective Function

The objective function of the bilevel problem is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
f^B = & \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{j \in J} C_j g_j + \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{j \in J} (C_j^+ g_{j\omega't}^+ - C_j^- g_{j\omega't}^-) + \sum_{n_g \in N^G} C^{\text{sh},g} l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh},g} \right] - \\
& \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n_g \in N^G} \left[\lambda_{n_g,t}^g \left(D_{n_g t}^g + \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_i p_{it}^* \right) + \sum_c \lambda_{n_g c}^c \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_i p_{ict}^{c*} \right] - \\
& \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n_g \in N^G} \left[\lambda_{n_g\omega t}^g \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_{i_g} \left(\psi_i^+ p_{it\omega}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{it\omega}^- \right) + \sum_c \lambda_{n_g c}^c \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_i \left(p_{ict\omega}^{c+} - p_{ict\omega}^{c-} \right) \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

The objective function contains the nonlinear product of the gas/contract prices and the generator production. We start by grouping the non-linear terms into a variable f^{NL} given as

$$\begin{aligned}
f^{\text{NL}} = & \sum_t \sum_{n_g \in N^G} \left[\lambda_{n_g,t}^g \left(\sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_i p_{it}^* \right) + \sum_c \lambda_{n_g c}^c \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_i p_{ict}^{c*} \right] + \\
& \sum_t \sum_{n_g \in N^G} \left[\lambda_{n_g\omega t}^g \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_{i_g} \left(\psi_i^+ p_{it\omega}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{it\omega}^- \right) + \sum_c \lambda_{n_g c}^c \sum_{i_g \in \mathcal{M}_{n_g}^{IG}} \eta_i \left(p_{ict\omega}^{c+} - p_{ict\omega}^{c-} \right) \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Now the bilevel objective can be written as

$$f^B = \sum_{t \in T} \sum_j C_j g_j + \sum_t \left[\sum_{j \in J} (C_j^+ g_{j\omega't}^+ - C_j^- g_{j\omega't}^-) - \sum_{n_g \in N^G} C^{\text{sh},g} l_{n_g\omega't}^{\text{sh},g} \right] - \sum_t \sum_{n_g \in N^G} \lambda_{n_g,t}^g \left(D_{n_g t}^g \right) - f^{\text{NL}} \tag{17}$$

The nonlinear term can be linearized using the strong duality of the electricity system dispatch problem. The primal objective function $f^{P,\text{elec}}$ of the electricity dispatch problem is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
f^{P,\text{elec}} = & \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i p_{it} + \sum_{i \in I^G} \left(\sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g t}^g \eta_i p_{it} + \sum_c \sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \lambda_{n_g c}^c \eta_i p_{ict}^c \right) \right] + \\
& \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \pi_\omega \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i \left(\psi_i^+ p_{i\omega t}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{i\omega t}^- \right) + C^{\text{sh},e} l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} + \right. \\
& \left. \sum_{i \in I^G} \left[\sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g\omega t}^g \eta_i \left(\psi_i^+ p_{i\omega t}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{i\omega t}^- \right) + \sum_c \sum_{n_g} \mathcal{M}_i^{n_g} \hat{\lambda}_{n_g c}^c \eta_i \left(p_{ic\omega t}^{c+} - p_{ic\omega t}^{c-} \right) \right] \right],
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

and its dual objective function $f^{D,\text{elec}}$ (which is linear) as

$$\begin{aligned}
f^{D,\text{elec}} = & - \sum_t \bar{\mu}_t^w \bar{W} - \sum_t \sum_i \left(\bar{\mu}_{it}^p (\bar{p}_i - \sum_c u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}c} \bar{p}_{ic}^c) - \sum_t \sum_\omega (\bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^w W_{\omega t} + \bar{\mu}_{\omega t}^l D_t^e) - \right. \\
& \left. \sum_t \sum_i \sum_c \left(\bar{v}_{itc} u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}c} \bar{p}_{ict}^c - \underline{v}_{itc} u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}c} \underline{p}_{ict}^c + \bar{v}_{itc}^+ u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}c} \bar{p}_{ict}^c + \bar{v}_{itc}^- u_c \mathcal{V}_{ict}^{\text{ON}c} \underline{p}_{ict}^c \right) \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

The primal objective function can be rewritten using (16) as

$$f^{P,\text{elec}} = \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i p_{it} + \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \pi_\omega \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i \left(\psi_i^+ p_{i\omega t}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{i\omega t}^- \right) + C^{\text{sh},e} l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} \right] + f^{\text{NL}}. \tag{20}$$

Next, we can apply the strong duality theory to rewrite the nonlinear term (16)

$$\begin{aligned}
f^{D,\text{elec}} &= \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i p_{it} + \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \pi_{\omega} \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i \left(\psi_i^+ p_{i\omega t}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{i\omega t}^- \right) + C^{\text{sh,e}} l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} \right] + f^{\text{NL}} \\
f^{\text{NL}} &= f^{D,\text{elec}} - \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i p_{it} - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \pi_{\omega} \sum_{t \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in I^{\text{NG}}} C_i \left(\psi_i^+ p_{i\omega t}^+ - \psi_i^- p_{i\omega t}^- \right) + C^{\text{sh,e}} l_{\omega t}^{\text{sh}} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

This expression can be substituted into (17) to obtain a linear objective function.

2 Case Study

2.1 Case Study I

The data that is used for the first case study is given in the tables below.

Table 1: Generation Assets

Name	Primary Fuel	Capacity [MW]	Linear Cost [€/MWh]	Heat Rate [MW/kNm ³]	Gas Node	ψ^+	ψ^+
i_1	Gas	150	-	8	ng101	1.1	0.92
w	wind	30	-	-	-	-	-

Table 2: Wind Scenario Probability

Name	Probability
ω_1^w	0.5
ω_2^w	0.5

Table 3: Electrical Load Data

Time	Load [MW]
t_1	50

Table 4: Wind Scenario Data

Time	ω_1^w [pu]	ω_2^w [pu]
t_1	0.8	0.2

Table 5: Contracts Offered

Contract	\underline{p}^c [MW]	\bar{p}^c [MW]	λ_c [€/kNm ³]
c_1	10	10	2.03
c_2	10	20	2.12
c_3	10	30	2.19

Table 6: Day-Ahead Gas Price Forecast

Time	$\hat{\lambda}^g$ [€/kNm ³]
t_1	2.03

Table 7: Real Time Gas Price Forecast

Time	$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_L}^g$ [€/kNm ³]	$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_M}^g$ [€/kNm ³]	$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_H}^g$ [€/kNm ³]
t_1	1.42	2.03	2.64

Table 8: Real Time Gas Price Probability

$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_L}^g$	$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_M}^g$	$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_H}^g$
1/3	1/3	1/3

Table 9: Gas Wells

Name	Gas Node	Min Production [kNm ³]	Max Production [kNm ³]	Linear Cost [€/ kNm ³]
j_1	n_{g_1}	0	224	1.9
j_2	n_{g_1}	0	96	2
j_3	n_{g_1}	0	800	1.1

Table 10: Nodal Gas Demand

Time	Load [kNm ³]
t_1	0

2.2 Case Study II

The data used in the second case study is given in the tables below and in the accompanying csv files. The wind and load profiles for this test case are based on the data from [1] and [2] and can be obtained at [3].

Table 11: Generation Assets

Name	Primary Fuel	Capacity [MW]	Linear Cost [€/MWh]	Heat Rate [MW/kNm ³]	Gas Node	ψ^+	ψ^-
i_1	gas	20	-	8	n_{g_1}	1.1	0.92
i_2	gas	25	-	8	n_{g_2}	1.1	0.92
i_3	nongas	15	5.2	-	-	1.1	0.92
i_4	nongas	150	100	-	-	1.1	0.92
w	wind	30	-	-	-	-	-

Table 12: Wind Scenario Probability

Name	Probability
ω_1^w	0.5
ω_2^w	0.5

Table 13: Real Time Gas Price Probability

$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_L}^g$	$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_M}^g$	$\hat{\lambda}_{\omega_H}^g$
1/3	1/3	1/3

Table 14: Gas Pipelines

Name	From Gas Node	To Gas Node	Capacity [kNm ³]
ℓ_1	n_{g_1}	n_{g_2}	10000

Table 15: Gas Wells

Name	Gas Node	Min Production [kNm ³]	Max Production [kNm ³]	Linear Cost [€/ kNm ³]
j_1	n_{g_1}	0	200	2
j_2	n_{g_1}	0	80	2.1
j_3	n_{g_1}	0	200	2.2
j_4	n_{g_1}	0	2000	2.3

References

- [1] W. A. Bukhsh, C. Zhang, P. Pinson, An integrated multiperiod OPF model with demand response and renewable generation uncertainty, IEEE Transactions on Smart Grids, Dec. 2015
- [2] P. Pinson, Wind energy: Forecasting challenges for its operational management, Statistical Science, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 564-585, 11, 2013
- [3] W. Bukhsh, 'Data for stochastic multiperiod optimal power flow problem', Website, Mar. 2017, <https://sites.google.com/site/datasmopf>